

RESEARCH TO DETERMINE THE CONTENT OF HISTORY

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Annotation. This in the article, in Uzbekistan medium special knowledgeable culture employees preparation from history data given .

Key words : Clubs , libraries , red teahouses , communist universities , Soviet and party schools , short term courses , pedagogy knowledge countries , technical schools , education countries , workers schools , book technical school , cinema and radio engineering knowledge country graduates .

of history content determination on the way research , or another word with describe sure If so , history inside correction came events and historical attacks with depends has been one scientific and methodical operation and scientific society with does This is historical the trip sending person , own in time , mutually connections analysis does and them looking for constant processes learning and in learning another to knowledge thin traits use with to pull continue to continue need has been It is known that it is historical in context there is . mental reality immediately swallowing and such thin knowledge exercise intensive ratification provide

of history content on the way research own especially in them historical the facts and literature objects does not show , maybe one series union provided of information reading to defeat have was xyrogen historical materials based on done is increased . about Har one content improve for , criticized work from learning first this materials historical mechanisms , from politics power effects , social , political and cultural affairs , read defeated one series topic definition and concepts to us in historical order stud to take down movement to do need

of history content on the way research for , ana that's it thinking , methodical tough-minded the work take will go and to give for literature in his work rising all intervals , material , all similarity in images robust manification with depends affairs will be done . I'm sorry if not built scientific researchers , experts define " bowed down " . acceptance if he does , they one historical analytical payment from order sure to determine his we create

of history content history on the way research based on , meaningful hearings and etakhos growth for consecutively . This factor with we with of help historical from the effects to see for commented Commentary need will be , and good critical one aspect excitement will be was

of history content on the way research action in negotiations sports barva and universal avyuz to work appear otherwise , theoretical impossible pump help zus:intifik free

Historians historical event and of events content and content in opening different of methods they use These are methods to historians the past more more efficient to understand and historical events right statement to do help will give .

History of science content in determining historians who uses of methods one primary sources research reach and analysis is to do Primary sources diary , letters , official documents such as event and of events the first from his hand received is information . This primary sources study through historians historical of individuals motives , beliefs and behavior about to understanding have to be , past about valuable information to open can

Historians history content in determining who uses again one method second level sources is learning . Secondary sources historical event and of events another historians by interpretation and are analyses . Secondary to sources appeal to do through historians historical to events differently point of view look and to interpretations have to be it is possible while them the past about more complete the concept to form help will give .

Historians history content in determining comparative analysis also use the method . Comparative analysis different historical event and events to compare and opposite put , laws , connections and similarities to determine own into takes Comparative analysis to do through historians in history trend and developments identify to get , past complexities deeper understandings can

Historians history content in determining used again one method interdisciplinary of approaches is to use . Historians most of the time anthropology , sociology and political science such as another in the fields specialists with historical to events different point of view look and to concepts have to be for cooperation they do Interdisciplinary approaches in himself embodied without historians the past about more complete to understanding have to be and historical events about more precisely information to give can

of history content in determining historians sweet tooth history also use the method . Oral history historical events directly saw or from the head forgave persons with the conversation own into takes The mouth is sweet history collect and analysis to do through historians separately of individuals views and experiences about unique to concepts have to be , past about written in sources rare valuable information to open can

Historians history content in determining used again one method archaeological from the evidence is to use . Archaeological evidence in the past from societies artifacts , constructions and another physical leftovers own into takes Archaeological the evidence research to do and comment through historians historical of societies diary life , beliefs and practice about to understanding have to be and written in sources rare the past about valuable information to open can

Historians history content in determining contextual analysis also use the method . Contextual analysis historical event and events wider social , cultural and political in contexts to learn own into takes Historical events happen was the conditions learning through historians historical of individuals motives , beliefs and behavior deeper understand the past more correct interpretation to do can

Historians history content in determining used again one method digital humanitarian from the sciences is to use . Digital humanitarian sciences historical data and information analysis do , interpret and present reach for digital tools and from technologies to use own into takes Digital humanitarian sciences own to research input through historians historical events about new to concepts have to be , in the past hidden connections and patterns to open and of history more interesting and interactive accounts present reach can

Summary by doing that's it to say maybe history of science content in determining historians primary and second level sources research to do and analysis do , comparative analysis , interdisciplinary approaches , oral history , archeology , contextual analysis and digital humanitarian sciences own into received different of methods they use These methods to apply through historians the past more complete understanding , historical events more correct statement achievements of history complexities with new and innovative methods with engage in can

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